

Correlation Analysis of Manual and Automatic FGA Assessment Using Pressure wellness mat Metrics*

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Abstract— FGA is a widely used clinical tool to assess dynamic balance and gait in individuals with a wide range of mobility disorders. This study explores the relationship between manual FGA ratings provided by clinical observers and automatic FGA assessment calculated using a pressure mat. Six participants performed the tasks of FGA balance test, including walking at different speeds, head turns, and obstacle stepping. Three expert clinicians independently scored participants' performance. Meanwhile, concurrent automated metrics were generated from an algorithm utilizing the pressure data given by the pressure mat readings. Manual and automated scores for FGA revealed a strong positive correlation with an ICC score of 0.783, indicating the feasibility of automatically calculating the FGA score using a pressure mat.

Clinical Relevance— The automatic assessment of the FGA with the pressure mat provides an objective and consistent scoring of the FGA, reducing the variability of manual assessments. Its high correlation with clinician scores highlights its potential to enhance balance and gait analysis precision and improve rehabilitation monitoring, ultimately benefiting patient outcomes in clinical practice.

I. INTRODUCTION

Balance is crucial for functional movement and independence and balance disorders can cause symptoms of vertigo, unsteadiness, dizziness, nausea and disequilibrium [1]. Balance and gait are important considerations in the health. It is estimated that 13% of older adults' self-report imbalance from ages 65 to 69 and this proportion increases to 46% in those aged 85 and older. Similarly, it is estimated that the prevalence of gait disorders in community-dwelling elderly adults aged 70 and older is 35% [2].

The Functional Gait Assessment (FGA) is a widely utilized clinical assessment of dynamic balance and gait for the purpose of identifying individuals at an increased risk of falls. It has high reliability, internal consistency, concurrent validity, and predictive validity [3]. Yet, its application region requires physiotherapists with the relevant experience.

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Developments in sensor technologies, such as pressure mats, provide automatic alternatives to gait assessment. These devices provide objective parameters related to quantitative analyses of gait and balance, pressure distribution, weight shift, center of pressure trajectory, among other metrics. To the best of the authors knowledge, it has not yet been investigated whether pressure mats are indeed able to replicate or replace manual FGA scoring. This study aims to analyze the correlation between manual FGA scoring by clinicians and automated scoring derived from mat data. The methodology involves processing pressure mat data to extract gait parameters and comparing them with clinician-assigned scores. By comparing the two approaches, we seek to evaluate the reliability of automated assessments and their potential to enhance clinical workflows and patient outcomes, by providing objectivity to the assessment process. This approach represents an advancement in automated gait analysis, reducing subjectivity and improving efficiency in clinical evaluations.

II. STATE OF THE ART

Functional gait and mobility assessment is crucial for fall risk and mobility impairment in older adults. Traditional assessments, like Functional Gait Assessment (FGA), rely on clinician observations to score balance, gait speed, and adaptation capabilities, requiring expertise.

Technological advances are automating assessments by using mobility aids with pressure-sensitive instruments and pads, measuring grip pressure, axial load and acceleration during gait tasks and predicting fall risk [4]. Similarly, systems such as the GAITRite [5] walkway and in-shoe pressure sensors have been used to capture spatiotemporal gait data with good reliability and agreement with clinical observations. Such systems are often limited to use in a laboratory.

Recent efforts focus on integrating machine learning and AI to further improve precision and applicability for automated gait assessments. For example, GaitKeeper [6], an

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AI-enabled system, has shown a high degree of gait parameter detection accuracy across a wide array of populations with promising potential in telehealth and continuous monitoring applications. Despite these advancements, challenges remain, especially in ensuring the reliability of automated systems across diverse conditions and populations [3].

The correlation between manual FGA scores and these systems still needs further validation to address the limitations of standardization of sensor output, real-world adjustment, and user compliance [7], [8]. In this paper, the psychometric properties of the FGA assessment are further enhanced by combining manual and automated approaches to improve reliability, reduce subjectivity, and provide objective gait evaluations.

III. MATERIALS & METHODOLOGY

A. Participants

Six healthy participants (3 male, 3 female), aged 25-40 years (mean age 27.83 ± 2.11 years), were recruited for the study. Data collection was carried out at the Orthopaedic Clinic, School of Medicine, University of Ioannina, in December 2024. The participants were selected via convenience and purposive sampling and provided informed consent before participation. They were included if they were considered healthy, with no previous issues performing exercises from the FGA assessment, as determined through self-reporting during recruitment. Three clinicians independently scored the participants' performance using the FGA: B. N., a chartered physiotherapist from University College London; I. W., from the Medical Center, University of Freiburg; and C. N., a registered physiotherapist from National and Kapodistrian University of Athens.

B. Equipment

FGA: The FGA, a clinical tool for assessing dynamic balance and gait, was used for manual assessments by clinicians. The test consists of ten tasks, with a scoring scale of 0 to 3. In this study, only 9 out of the 10 tasks were used (Fig. 1), as the 10th task involves climbing and descending a staircase, which was not safe via a pressure mat. Using only 9/10 tasks, a proportional adjustment of the standard FGA cut-off score was applied, resulting in a modified threshold of $\leq 19/27$ for classifying fall risk.

Figure 1. FGA: Test Items, Scoring, and Fall Risk Interpretation.

Pressure wellness mat: For the automatic assessment, the Sensing Tex pressure mat [9] was used. The pressure mat has 2,304 sensors for detailed high resolution data collection across the surface. The system continuously captures and visualizes real-time pressure data, with weight distribution, postural stability, and gait dynamics information. In this

study, six individual pressure mats were combined for the 6m length required for the FGA tasks.

Software: In-house software was used to combine the six mats', ensuring comprehensive coverage of the walking path while maintaining data integrity. The software provides real-time data by aligning timestamps for each mat to avoid any gaps or overlaps in recorded steps. It balances the pressure readings on all mats to ensure they measure the same parameter consistently while correcting for possible differences in calibration between sensors.

System Dashboard: The system dashboard provides a comprehensive analysis of gait metrics using data captured from the pressure mat. A one-step clustering algorithm identifies neighboring high-pressure points to extract cluster steps. This algorithm groups pressure points according to their spatial proximity and their intensity to accurately count legitimate steps while filtering out random noise. Furthermore, it dynamically adjusts to changes in foot pressure, giving it more strength to detect aberrant gait patterns. Thus, the system is capable of accurately detecting and segmenting gait cycles.

The results are represented on the dashboard for several key areas, as shown in Fig. 2. First, it provides an overview of metrics, giving a graphical overview of average cadence and step counts in three dimensions. Then, it calculates Gait Cycle Metrics: cadence, single-support time, and double-support time for each gait cycle visualized with interactive graphs. These estimates are based on pressure data that is time-stamped with specific identification of the start and end of each step, in order to make calculations of cycle duration and support phase. Finally, it calculates the mean horizontal and vertical displacements during gait cycles by assessing foot placement coordinates and the displacement between consecutive steps. Such analysis gives insight into the stride variability and balance.

Figure 2. FGA Assessment Dashboard.

Finally, the pressure mat visualization (Fig. 3) displays footprint patterns where regions of higher pressure are marked with red reflecting increased force in every step. This further supports the analysis of gait symmetry, stability and deviations to better understand patient performance.

Figure 3. Pressure wellness mat visualization.

C. Data collection

Participants performed the 9 tasks outlined in the FGA, including walking at different speeds, turning, and using head movements. For this purpose, the pressure mat was 6m in total length and marked with a 30.48 cm width, as provided by the FGA questionnaire (Fig. 4). The tasks were conducted in a controlled environment and participants received standardized instructions before each task to reduce potential bias. Each exercise was video recorded, and clinicians evaluated them on a later stage. These scores were later analysed to determine the level of agreement between clinicians and the pressure mat algorithm to identify any differences in scoring patterns. The study aimed to: i) provide information on the reliability of the FGA tool when used by different raters and, ii) compare manual scoring with an automatic assessment via the pressure mat.

Figure 4. (a) Simulated Setup, (b) Experimental Setup for Gait Assessment Using Pressure wellness mat and 6m Corridor. (c) Pressure wellness mat.

D. Manual Assessment

Three expert clinicians, blinded to the evaluations of each other, independently reviewed the videos and scored the participants on the FGA scale. The clinicians followed standardized scoring guidelines (0–3 for each task) in the FGA manual to ensure uniformity in their assessments.

E. System for Automatic Assessment

The automatic assessment of the FGA tasks was performed by analyzing data collected from the pressure mat. Key gait metrics, such as gait speed, step length, center of pressure (CoP) variability, path deviation, and step height, were

measured during task execution. Each task was scored on a four-point scale, from 0-3 based on predefined thresholds, negotiated with clinicians and based on current evidence. The scores correspond to levels of dysfunction: normal (3), mild (2), moderate (1) and severe impairment (0). These thresholds are outlined in Table I, where each task is associated with specific metrics and criteria.

TABLE I. METRICS AND THRESHOLDS.

FGA	Metric/Score	3	2	1	0
1	Gait Speed (m/s)	> 0.8 m/s	0.6–0.8 m/s	0.4–0.6 m/s	< 0.4 m/s
	Step Length (m)	> 0.6 m	0.4–0.6 m	0.3–0.4 m	< 0.3 m
	CoP Variability (mm)	< 10 mm	10–20 mm	20–30 mm	> 30 mm
2	Speed Variability (%)	< 10%	10–20%	> 20%	Cannot adjust speed
	Adaptation Time (s)	< 1.2 s	1.2–1.8 s	> 1.8 s	Cannot adapt
3	Path Deviation (%)	< 5%	5–15%	15–30%	> 30%
	Reaction Time (s)	< 0.6 s	0.6–1.0 s	> 1.0 s	Cannot react
4	Path Deviation (%)	< 5%	5–15%	15–30%	> 30%
5	Number of Steps to Turn	≤ 2 steps	3–4 steps	5–6 steps	> 6 steps or cannot complete
6	Step Height (cm)	> 12 cm	8–12 cm	5–8 cm	< 5 cm or contacts obstacle
	Path Linearity (%)	< 5% deviation	5–15%	15–30%	> 30%
7	Step Width Variability (m)	< 0.1 m	0.1–0.2 m	0.2–0.3 m	> 0.3 m
8	Path Deviation (%)	< 5%	5–15%	15–30%	> 30% or loses balance
9	Backward Gait Speed (m/s)	> 0.5 m/s	0.4–0.5 m/s	0.3–0.4 m/s	< 0.3 m/s
	CoP Variability (mm)	< 15 mm	15–25 mm	25–35 mm	> 35 mm

IV. RESULTS

The study compares manual FGA scores from three observers and automated scores from the pressure mat system. Table II presents the individual scores of all participants.

TABLE II. INDIVIDUAL FGA SCORES FOR PARTICIPANTS.

Participant	Observer1	Observer2	Observer3	System
ID 1	21	23	18	22
ID 2	26	27	25	25
ID 3	25	26	20	24
ID 4	24	26	18	26
ID 5	24	25	18	24
ID 6	23	27	17	25

Observer 1's scores ranged from 21 to 26 (SD=1.72), Observer 2's from 23 to 27 (SD=1.51), and Observer 3's (SD=2.94) from 17 to 25, showing variability in the manual scores. The automated system scored 22 to 26 (SD = 1.37) and generally fell within the range of the manual scores. For instance, Participant ID 2 scored 25 by the system, which agreed with Observer 3, and was one point lower than Observer 2, and one point higher than Observer 1. This pattern reflects how the automated system mostly agrees with the general average of the manual scores.

Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) was calculated to represent the consistency of manual scorers. The ICC score between the three observers was 0.770, while an ICC score of 0.783 indicates significant agreement between the observers and the system. This value was computed using IBM SPSS [10] with a Two-Way Random Effects Model, which assesses absolute agreement among raters and the system. There are, however, variations between different scorers, for instance, observer 3 and observer 2, which reflect their inherent subjectivity. The automatic system showed consistent results with the average of all manual assessments (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Scores by Observers and System and the ICC value.

V. DISCUSSION

The study reveals a strong correlation between clinician's manual FGA assessments by clinicians and automated evaluations using the pressure mat system. Although there is variability between manual observers, the ICC value of 0.783 supports the reliability of automatic scoring. However, manual scoring's subjective nature can introduce variability.

Results align with previous research demonstrating the effectiveness of sensor-based gait analysis in supplementing manual assessments. The pressure mat performed comparably to GAITRite and in-shoe pressure sensors in capturing reliable gait metrics. Unlike lab-restricted systems, its portability allows for broader clinical and real-world use.

An automated system integrated into FGA assessments will enhance clinical efficiency by reducing subjectivity and allowing repeatable, data-driven evaluations. Clinicians can track subtle gait changes over time aiding early detection of mobility impairments and optimizing rehabilitation strategies. Minimizing observer-dependent variability, the system can improve diagnostic accuracy and treatment planning.

The pressure mat offers real-time data processing and the ability to detect subtle gait abnormalities, providing expert

clinical judgment and repeatable, unbiased scoring, unlike manual assessments that require expert judgment.

Despite its advantages, the pressure mat system has limitations. Pressure distribution depends on walking surface, and individual gait pattern affecting measurement accuracy. Integrating IMUs, placed in the lower limbs, could enhance gait analysis by measuring a broader range of motion metrics.

Overall, the study highlights the feasibility of using the pressure mat algorithm to enhance manual FGA assessments by improving objective data collection, ensuring consistency, and reducing rater bias.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates a strong correlation between the manual and automatic FGA scores, justifying the use of pressure mat's for enhancing FGA assessment scoring. These findings indicate that pressure mats can be used as a valid, reliable and objective alternative to manual scoring to reduce subjectivity and rate bias. Furthermore, this can increase clinical efficiency in the clinical setting. Future research will explore a data-driven FGA approach using machine learning models and IMU sensors for precise gait pattern detection, improving accuracy, scalability, and utility of automated gait analysis systems for clinical and research purposes.

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